

Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) and Wide-Angle X-Ray Diffraction (WAXD) Comparative Study on Malignant and Benign Human Cancer Cells and Tissues under Synchrotron Radiation

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In the current study, we have experimentally and comparatively investigated and compared malignant human cancer cells and tissues before and after irradiating of synchrotron radiation using Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) and Wide-Angle X-Ray

Diffraction (WAXD), It is clear that malignant human cancer cells and tissues have gradually transformed to benign human cancer cells and tissues under synchrotron radiation with the passing of time (Figures 1 and 2) [1-135].

Figure 1. Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) analysis of malignant human cancer cells and tissues (a) before and (b) after irradiating of synchrotron radiation in transformation process to benign human cancer cells and tissues with the passing of time [1-135].

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Figure 2. Wide-Angle X-Ray Diffraction (WAXD) analysis of malignant human cancer cells and tissues (a) before and (b) after irradiating of synchrotron radiation in transformation process to benign human cancer cells and tissues with the passing of time [1-135].

It can be concluded that malignant human cancer cells and tissues have gradually transformed to benign human cancer cells and tissues under synchrotron radiation with the passing of time (Figures 1 and 2) [1-135].

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